

MALE NURSES' INTENTION TO STAY IN A SPECIFIC HOSPITAL: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to understand factors contributing to male nurses' retention and satisfaction in a government-owned hospital setting in the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao. Utilizing qualitative case study, the research employed purposive sampling to identify male nurses who committed to stay and work in a hospital. In-depth interviews were conducted with 11 registered male nurses, each having over five years of experience and currently working at said hospital. The researchers followed the Creswell and Creswell's (2018) five steps during data analysis process: 1. Organize and prepare the data for analysis, 2. Read or look at all the data, 3. Start coding all of the data, 4. Generate a description and themes, 5. Representing the description and themes. The findings revealed three key themes: reasons for selecting a specific hospital, factors influencing long-term commitment, and solutions to interpersonal conflicts. The study concludes that male nurses' decisions to remain at a particular hospital are influenced by their satisfaction with salary and other work benefits, prospects for growth and development, camaraderie among staff, and the ability to remain neutral and fair during interpersonal conflict situations.

Keywords: *Intention to stay, male nurses, retention, Filipino, commitment, case study*

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the nursing profession has witnessed a notable demographic shift, with an increasing number of men entering what was traditionally considered a female-

dominated field. This trend has been particularly evident since the 1970s, and currently male nurses comprise more than 13% of the overall nursing workforce (American Nurses Association, 2023). The decision-making process for men pursuing a nursing career remains influenced by various factors such as societal expectations, childhood experiences, perceptions on nurses' challenges, and other positive aspects within the profession (Dos Santos, 2020; Banakhar et al., 2021).

As men enter the nursing profession, they bring with them unique characteristics and qualities, including caring, calmness, attentiveness, bravery, and skill (Kaur et al., 2022). Additionally, male nurses exhibit autonomy in decision-making, emotional resilience, a sense of humor, and they demonstrate respect, consideration, and supportiveness towards patients (Saleh et al., 2020; Martínez-Morato et al., 2021; Sundus & Younas, 2020; Mao et al., 2021). Despite these positive attributes, male nurses also encounter challenges within their working environments, ranging from limitations in job performance to gender-based discrimination (Shin & Lim, 2021; Chang & Jeong, 2021; Papantoniou, 2021).

Moreover, job satisfaction among male nurses is influenced by various factors, including personality, resilience, emotional intelligence, mental well-being, stress, and organizational factors such as leadership styles and organizational culture (Nam & Kim, 2018; Kim et al., 2019; Chang & Kim, 2022). Notably, the intention of male nurses to remain in a specific hospital is shaped by factors such as work commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational factors like hospital type and salaries (Labrague et al., 2018; Sagar & Oducado, 2021).

While the existing literature provides valuable insights into various aspects of male nurses' experiences, challenges, and motivations, there remains a research gap concerning their intention to stay in a specific hospital, particularly within the confines of government-run hospitals in the Philippines. Existing studies either offer generalized perspectives or focus on broader organizational commitment, failing to delve into the intricate dynamics of male nurses' retention within a specific hospital.

Hence, this study addressed three gaps. First, it addressed the knowledge gap by specifically examining the possible reasons for male nurses' intention to remain within a specific hospital in the Philippines. Second, it addressed a methodological gap by utilizing a qualitative research design. A broader understanding of factors influencing their intention to stay within their respective hospital in this specific geographical setting is necessary. Third, it addressed a population gap in existing research on the intention of male nurses to stay in a specific hospital. By focusing on the insufficiently researched population of male nurses in government-run hospitals in Region X, Mindanao, Philippines, the study sought to enhance our knowledge and offer insights into the factors influencing the retention patterns of male nurses in a particular hospital. This study aimed to explore deeper insights into reasons for male nurses' intention to remain working in a hospital in the Philippines. Hospital managers and nurse administrators can draw insights useful in crafting retention and job satisfaction policies and strategies for male nurses in similar hospital settings in the Philippines, particularly in Mindanao.

Research Questions

The main research questions were:

1. What are the male nurses' reasons for selecting a specific hospital?
2. What motivates male nurses in maintaining their dedication to a specific hospital over an extended period of time?
3. How do male nurses manage and address interpersonal conflicts within their departments?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers of this study used the qualitative case study design as the suitable approach for this research. Case studies are empirical inquiries that investigated a phenomenon in its real-life context (Yin, 2009). A case study can be descriptive, explanatory, or exploratory (Yin, 2014). Case studies are useful for answering “how” and “why” questions about a set of events over which the researchers have little or no control (Yin, 2009). These studies are bounded by the unique characteristics and complexities of the particular case being studied, and it is important to understand the individual case within its specific context rather than attempt to generalize findings to other cases or contexts (Stake, 1995). In this study, the phenomenon under investigation covered the multiple complexities forming the reasons or factors that influenced male nurses' stays in a specific hospital.

Bounded System and Participants

The case of this study included registered male nurses currently working at a government-run and tertiary hospital in Region X, Mindanao, Philippines. The study involved 11 male registered nurses from Gregorio T. Lluh Memorial Hospital (GTLMH) in Iligan City, Lanao del Norte, each with a minimum of 5 years of work experience. A purposive sampling strategy, particularly criterion sampling, was employed to select participants based on the inclusion criteria: male gender, at least 5 years of work experience at GTLMH, and registered nurse status.

Semi-Structured Interview Protocol

This study utilized semi-structured interviews that allowed the researchers to delve into the factors that affect male nurses in staying in a specific hospital. The interviews were tailored to capture nuances and contextual details, fostering open conversations that reveal participants' thoughts, feelings, and personal reflections on their work experience in the chosen hospital in Iligan City. Participant observation was used, which offered an immersive lens into how male interact with their fellow nurses and patients.

Ethical Considerations

Several ethical considerations were taken into account. Primarily, permission from the hospital's administrator and head nurse was obtained through a letter of authorization in order to gain access to the institution's employees, which ensured the researchers' credibility. The research used "informed consent" approach so that the participants would be aware of the purpose and research design. Participants' confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed, and permission to audio record the interviews were granted by the participants through the consent form.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before data collection, the researchers sought clearance from the Ethics Review Committee of Adventist Medical Center College. Participants were carefully selected, informed of the study's purpose, and assured of confidentiality before providing consent. Interviews were scheduled at convenient times and locations within the hospital, and conducted using a semi-structured format to cover key topics while allowing open-ended response. The interviewer built rapport, paid attention to nonverbal cues, and asked clarifying questions. With participants' consent, interviews were audio-recorded and supplemental field notes. During and after the interviews, the researchers wrote memos and updated entries in the audit trail. Transcripts were verified by participants, ensuring accuracy. Data were securely stored, anonymized, and analyzed thematically, with findings triangulated for credibility. Table 1 shows a data triangulation matrix.

Table 1

Data Triangulation Matrix

<i>Research Questions</i>	<i>Source 1</i>	<i>Source 2</i>
RQ1: What are the male nurses' reasons for selecting a specific hospital?	Participant Interview	Observation
RQ2: What motivates male nurses in maintaining their dedication to a specific hospital over an extended period of time?	Participant Interview	Observation
RQ3: How do male nurses manage and address interpersonal conflicts within their departments?	Participant Interview	Observation

Data Analysis

In qualitative research, data analysis progresses alongside the other components of the study, such as data collection and reporting findings (Creswell & Creswell 2018). This type of research emphasizes using everyday methods of interpretation (Stake, 1995). After the interviews and the consequent transcriptions, member checking was achieved, and data analysis followed Creswell and Creswell's (2018) five steps to achieve codes and categorical themes.

Trustworthiness and Authenticity

Authenticity and trustworthiness were paramount considerations to ensure the credibility and reliability of the researcher's findings. Drawing on insights from Flory and Emanuel (2004) and Wilkinson and Kitzinger (2020), the researchers recognized the importance of transparency to enhance authenticity. To enhance the authenticity of the researcher's study findings, the researchers prioritized transparency and ethical conduct through adhering to the ethical considerations through informed consent.

Trustworthiness was also prioritized by employing strategies recommended by renowned qualitative researchers. To enhance credibility (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), the researchers *triangulated* data (Stake, 1995; Merriam, 2002; Yin, 2009) from multiple sources and performed *member checks* to validate the accuracy of the researchers' interpretations. The researchers also sought *peer review* to ensure the congruency of the findings with the data and interpretations and provided an *audit trail*, documenting the methods, procedures, and decision points throughout the research process to enhance dependability.

Furthermore, the researchers engaged in *reflexivity* (Merriam, 2002), critically reflecting on the researchers' assumptions, biases, and relationship to the study. This self-awareness enabled them to navigate potential biases effectively and produce a nuanced and insightful exploration of male nurses' intentions. In addition, the researchers ensured a *rich description* by providing detailed contextual information to enable readers to understand the study's context thoroughly. For example, the researchers described the participants' demographic characteristics, such as their assigned department, starting and current working position, years of experience, and marital status, as well as the setting in which the study took place, including the hospital's size, location, and organizational structure.

Additionally, the researchers incorporated *maximum variation* by recruiting participants from various departments in the hospital "to allow for a greater range of application of the findings by consumers of the research" (Merriam, 2002 p. 31). This deliberate sampling approach enhanced the richness and depth of the researcher's data, contributing to the credibility and transferability of the findings. By adhering to these principles of authenticity and trustworthiness, the researchers aimed to ensure the ethical conduct and reliability of the qualitative study. Through transparent documentation, critical reflection, and methodological rigor, the researchers sought to contribute to the body of knowledge on male nurses' intentions in the hospital setting with confidence and integrity.

Reflexivity Statement

It is clear that the primary instrument for data collection and analysis in qualitative research is the researcher herself. Qualitative research assumes that the researcher's biases and values impact the outcome of any study (Merriam, 1998). To enable any audience of qualitative studies to evaluate the validity of conclusions drawn from data,

researchers should, as part of the study, neutralize or bracket their biases by stating them explicitly to the full extent possible (Altheide & Johnson, 1994).

In this study, reflexivity was acknowledged to address potential biases stemming from our backgrounds and experiences. Firstly, the researchers status as nursing students may have provided them with insider knowledge of the nursing profession, including its challenges, dynamics, and gender disparities. Furthermore, the researchers observation of the scarcity of male nurses in various hospital departments and the researchers interactions with male classmates in the nursing program may have shaped their understanding of gender dynamics within the nursing profession.

RESULTS

Table 2 provides a demographic profile of participants, including their department, years of service, starting position, current position, and marital status. Participants represent a diverse range of departments and possess varying levels of experience, from 8 to 31 years.

Table 2
Participants' Demographic Profile

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Department</i>	<i>Years of Service</i>	<i>Starting Position</i>	<i>Current Position</i>	<i>Marital Status</i>
P001	Emergency Room	12	Job Order	Nurse I	Single
P002	Health Emergency Management Bureau Unit (HEMB)	31	Request of Employment	Nurse IV	Single
P003	Health Emergency Management Bureau Unit (HEMB)	24	Residency Training	Nurse II	Married

Table 2 (continued)

P004	Hemodialysis Unit	12	Job Order	Nurse II	Single
P005	Intensive Care Unit	18	Job Order	Regular Nurse	Married

P006	Out-patient Department	20	Request of Employment	Nurse II	Married
P007	Out-patient Department	30	Kitchen Staff	Nurse II	Married
P008	Operating Room	20	Residency Training	Contractual	Married
P009	Operating Room	8	Contractual	Contractual	Married
P010	Respiratory Unit	11	Staff Nurse	Nurse I	Single
P011	Surgery Ward	10	Staff Nurse	Staff Nurse	Single

During the interviews, participants were stationed within their respective departments and were informed in advance by their head nurses regarding the scheduled interviews. Despite this, they exhibited a welcoming demeanor and demonstrated cooperation throughout the process. Participants varied in their contributions to the three themes constituting the narrative. While some individuals extensively discussed one or two themes, others evenly distributed their input across all three. Consequently, the study ensured the representation of all participants' voices and perspectives.

The research findings are organized into three themes: (a) reasons for selecting a specific hospital, (b) factors influencing long-term commitment, and (c) interpersonal conflict's solutions. Each theme explores the experiences and perspectives of male nurses, offering insights into the complexities of their professional lives within the hospital setting.

Theme 1: Reasons in Selecting a Specific Hospital

Participants shared their motivations and considerations guiding them towards decisions when selecting a particular hospital for employment. It is focused on the primary factors that attract male nurses emphasizing beneficial offers such as experience, salary, and team-building activities.

Table 3***Beneficial Offers of the Hospital***

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Participant Interview</i>	<i>Observation</i>
Gaining experience	<i>"The reason why I applied here is because of my future work. I believe that this hospital offers a unique environment and opportunities that align closely with my professional goals and personal values. By working here, I aim to gain invaluable experience, refine my skills, and contribute meaningfully to the healthcare community."</i> (P009)	Enthusiasm and passion observed during the interview. Consistency in responses, emphasizing professional growth and contribution. Positive body language and confident tone.
Salary	<i>"The pay rate in government hospitals is generally higher compared to private ones."</i> (P002)	Participant mentioned specific figures or comparisons indicating awareness of salary differences.
Team-building	<i>"I enjoyed the company of my batchmates when I joined. We spent a longer period of time together, which strengthened our bond. Moreover, the hospital before used to organize team-building activities for all employees. There were days when the entire hospital would go for team-building outside the premises, like going to the beach."</i> (P002)	Described past team-building activities with enthusiasm and fondness. Provided specific examples of team-building events and their impact on morale. Positive demeanor when discussing team-building and social interactions.

Theme 2: Factors Influencing Long-Term Commitment

This theme explores the factors driving long-term commitment and dedication among male nurses, focusing on two key aspects: the prospect for career advancement and strong interpersonal connections. These elements resonate strongly with the majority of male nurses and significantly shape their commitment to their profession and workplace.

Prospect for Career Advancement

This theme encompasses factors influencing male nurses' perceptions of opportunities for professional growth and development within their careers. It includes components such as becoming resourceful and creative, experiencing learning opportunities, the prospect of growth and development, striving further to learn, and participating in trainings and seminars.

Table 4*Prospect for Career Advancement*

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Participant Interview</i>	<i>Observation</i>
Becoming resourceful and creative	<i>"Yes, despite the limitations in budget and resources, it pushes us to be more resourceful and creative in delivering care to our patients. This mindset cultivates resilience and adaptability, which are essential qualities for nurses in any healthcare setting."</i> (P004)	Described creative solutions they have implemented. Showed enthusiasm for challenges and problem-solving. Demonstrated resilience and adaptability in responses.
Experience learning opportunities	<i>"Despite the inherent difficulties, these experiences serve as invaluable learning opportunities, honing my interpersonal skills and enhancing my ability to provide compassionate care even in the most challenging circumstances."</i> (P001)	Exhibited a reflective attitude on personal growth. Showed a compassionate approach to patient care.
Prospect of growth and development	<i>"The prospect of growth and development within the hospital does play a role in my decision to stay for an extended duration. The knowledge that there are pathways for advancement and the possibility of taking on new challenges in the future adds a sense of purpose and direction to my tenure here."</i> (P001)	Participant discussed future career plans and advancement opportunities. Showed awareness of career pathways and developmental programs within the hospital. Expressed a clear sense of purpose and direction.
Striving further to learn	<i>"For me, despite the years I've spent, I still thrive on learning and there's so much more I want to learn."</i> (P010)	Shared excitement about new areas they want to explore. Demonstrated a lifelong learning attitude and continuous curiosity.
Trainings and seminars	<i>"Before, training here was fast-paced, which is why I was encouraged to stay."</i> (P007)	Answered the questions confidently and was able to share his experiences in his stay in the hospital.

Strong Interpersonal Connections

This theme explores the significance of social relationships and collaboration among male nurses in the workplace, focusing on camaraderie and bonding with colleagues and the value of teamwork.

Table 5
Strong Interpersonal Connections

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Participant Interview</i>	<i>Observation</i>
Camaraderie and bonding with colleagues	<i>"It's the people around me. Even if the salary is low, and it took a long time to receive payment when I started as a casual employee. I even started without pay, right? But despite that, it's really the people who are there. Yes, the bond. Even if we don't have much money, we can still eat together, have fun in our area, even if there are challenging patients or watchers, we continue. We can still manage to laugh and joke around because of the camaraderie and the people you work with." (P004)</i>	The casual joking and laughter exchanged among participants indicate a comfortable and positive atmosphere where colleagues feel at ease interacting with one another, fostering social cohesion and emotional well-being.
Value of teamwork	<i>"I value teamwork over personal convenience. In this hospital where staff is often insufficient, if you possess the necessary skills and knowledge, it's compassionate to assist your less skilled colleagues rather than leaving them behind." (P010)</i>	The researchers noted an instance where participant P010 provided guidance and assistance to a trainee under his supervision in communicating with a client, exemplifying his commitment to fostering a supportive work environment.

Theme 3: Interpersonal Conflict's Solutions

This theme explores the various methods male nurses utilize to navigate and resolve interpersonal conflicts encountered within healthcare environments. The predominant strategy observed across responses is the emphasis on maintaining neutrality and fairness in addressing such situations.

Neutrality and Fairness in Situations

This theme centers around the principles of impartiality, objectivity, and equitable treatment in addressing conflicts and reaching resolution. This focuses on giving time before resolving, helping each other out, leaving it to higher ups, not being one-sided, not harboring grudges, open-minded approach, and verifying situation.

Table 6
Neutrality and Fairness in Situations

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Participant Interview</i>	<i>Observation</i>
Giving time before resolving	<i>"Sometimes it's best to postpone it to let things cool down because everyone's still heated and emotions are running high, so it's better to calm down first as nothing gets resolved when everyone's just angry." (P004)</i>	Participant demonstrated a calm and measured demeanor during the interview. Showed awareness of emotional states and their impact on conflict resolution.
Helping each other out	<i>"In the OR, cleanliness is paramount. So if your teammate is lazy and doesn't work, it affects everyone, and it also affects the cleanliness of the OR. As a team, you should really help each other out." (P008)</i>	Talked about the importance of cleanliness and collaboration. Showed appreciation for team efforts and describes situations where helping each other improved outcomes.
Leaving it to higher ups	<i>"In disagreements, at the end of the day, it's usually the head who steps in to help resolve the issue." (P006)</i>	Showed reliance on hierarchical structure for resolving disputes.
Not being one-sided	<i>"Just provide solutions... It's important to remain neutral and accept all sides. Don't be one-sided." (P005)</i>	The researchers observed that positive relationships among coworkers demonstrated a commitment to fairness and neutrality in handling conflicts. Emphasized the value of considering all perspectives and avoiding bias.

Table 6 (continued)

Not harboring grudges	<i>"It just passes by... I'm not one to harbor grudges. So I haven't experienced conflicts."</i> (P007)	Participant exhibited a positive and forgiving attitude. Showed a lack of resentment and emphasizes moving on from disagreements.
Open-minded approach	<i>"If a conflict or disagreement arises, it's important to communicate. We need to talk about the differences, identify any mistakes, and understand the reasons behind them. Instead of letting things escalate without taking action, addressing the conflict head-on allows us to resolve issues and prevent them from worsening."</i> (P007)	Demonstrated a proactive attitude towards conflict resolution. Emphasized the importance of understanding the underlying reasons behind conflicts. Showed a belief in the effectiveness of open communication in resolving issues.
Verifying situation	<i>"I verify what really happened before saying anything. We shouldn't jump into conclusions without gathering all the data."</i> (P002)	Demonstrated a careful and analytical mindset when dealing with conflicts.

DISCUSSION

The findings reveal that male nurses intended to stay because of beneficial offers, opportunities for gaining experience, competitive salaries, and team-building activities. The desire for professional growth, stable income, and a supportive work environment significantly contributed to job satisfaction and retention intentions. The prospect of career advancement, continuous professional development through training and seminars, and strong interpersonal connections, described as akin to family, are crucial for long-term commitment. Participants also emphasized the importance of resourcefulness and creativity in patient care, viewing challenging interactions as valuable learning opportunities. Effective conflict resolution strategies include maintaining neutrality and fairness, giving time before addressing conflicts, involving higher-ups, and verifying situations to ensure fair outcomes. Overall, career progression opportunities, supportive work culture, and teamwork are critical in attracting, retaining, and ensuring long-term commitment among male nurses.

The researchers of this study found that job satisfaction and organizational commitment are crucial in nurses' retention. This finding joins the research of Dutta, Sutnga, and Kaur (2021) on job satisfaction among nurses that emphasized the role of

professional growth opportunities, echoing the participants' focus on gaining experience. Similarly, the study of Labrague et al. (2018) underscores the influence of salary and organizational factors on nurses' retention intentions, supporting the researchers participants' emphasis on competitive salaries. Participants preferred staying in the public or governmental hospital, which offers a higher pay rate than private sector. Furthermore, the researchers findings are consistent with earlier research in some aspects, but the researchers data revealed the value of team-building activities. Through team-building, camaraderie and social interaction occur, contributing to job satisfaction and creating supportive work environment for male nurses.

The prospect for career advancement and strong interpersonal connections influenced the long-term commitments among nurses in this hospital. Participants highlighted the practice of being resourceful and creative in patient care, viewing challenging interactions as valuable learning opportunities. The continuous professional growth through training and seminars facilitated their renewed sense of purpose and direction. A supportive work culture and camaraderie among colleagues was described as akin to family relationships. Teamwork and mutual assistance were highly valued, fostering a positive and cohesive work environment.

The researchers findings also uncovered various strategies for conflict resolution within healthcare settings. While previous studies have explored aspects of conflict resolution, emotional intelligence, and leadership's impact on organizational culture, the researchers study contributes nuanced insights into these areas. Chang and Kim (2022) discussed organizational culture and leadership broadly but did not delve into specific conflict resolution strategies. In contrast, this study offers practical methods for maintaining neutrality and fairness—giving time before resolving, helping each other out, leaving it to higher-ups, not being one-sided, not harboring grudges, an open-minded approach, and verifying situations—enriching the understanding of how these concepts manifest in real-world conflict scenarios. Additionally, while Liu et al. (2022) highlighted emotional intelligence's role in managing interpersonal challenges, our study goes further by providing concrete examples of its application, demonstrating its effectiveness in navigating conflicts among healthcare professionals.

Moreover, this study diverges from previous research by emphasizing the importance of teamwork as a conflict resolution strategy rather than solely focusing on interpersonal relationships as noted by Baker (2019). While Marañón, Rodríguez-Martín, and Galbany-Estragués (2019) explored professional-family relationships and gender dynamics, our findings underscore the significance of avoiding grudges and fostering professional relationships as crucial elements in resolving conflicts within healthcare teams. Furthermore, while Mao et al. (2020) prioritized maintaining respect and dignity in interactions, this study emphasizes the importance of fact-checking and due diligence in conflict resolution processes. Lastly, unlike Chang and Kim (2022), who primarily discussed leadership's influence on organizational commitment, this study highlights the practical involvement of higher-ups in resolving conflicts, offering tangible strategies for addressing conflicts within healthcare organizations.

The findings from this study carry significant implications for healthcare management and policy, particularly in crafting effective strategies for recruiting and retaining male nurses. By identifying specific factors that appeal to male nurses, such as competitive salaries, structured training programs, and team-building activities, healthcare administrators can tailor their recruitment efforts to better attract and retain this demographic. Moreover, the study highlights the pivotal role of professional growth opportunities and a supportive work environment in securing long-term commitment from male nurses. To address these needs, healthcare institutions may consider investing in continuous education programs and establishing clear pathways for career advancement.

Additionally, the study's emphasis on effective conflict resolution underscores the necessity for hospitals to offer training in interpersonal skills and conflict management for male nurses. By equipping male nurses with the tools to navigate and resolve conflicts efficiently, hospitals can foster a more harmonious and productive workplace. This is extremely important in public hospitals where the application of a neutral attitude towards work conflicts can enable one to navigate through the bureaucratic systems, and promote team harmony. Such an approach fosters strong interpersonal relationships, which is one of the key determinants as to why male nurses tend to stay long-term in any public hospital setting. Improved patient care outcomes can therefore be achieved through this since it always ensures a coherent and supportive working environment.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this research reveals a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the intention of male nurses to remain in a particular hospital. Key factors include the beneficial offerings provided by the hospital, such as work experience, salary, and team-building activities. Furthermore, factors influencing long-term commitment is influenced by prospects for career advancement, including opportunities for creativity, learning, growth, and development. Strong interpersonal connections, characterized by camaraderie and teamwork, are also highlighted as crucial for creating a supportive and collaborative work environment, essential for the well-being and success of male nurses.

Interpersonal conflict's solutions, particularly neutrality and fairness in situations are highlighted by giving time before resolving, helping each other out, leaving it to higher-ups, not being one-sided, not harboring grudges, open-minded approach and verifying the situation. The findings of our study highlight that male nurses' decision to remain in a particular hospital is driven by the strong interpersonal relationships and teamwork. In governmental hospitals, where politics influence work, male nurses adopt a neutral approach to conflicts, preventing bias and fostering harmonious relationships. This neutrality is key to resolving conflicts and maintaining strong relationships, which significantly influences their decision to stay long-term.

Recommendations

The researchers of this study recommends future research endeavors to implement several key strategies. Firstly, future researchers should consider broadening the scope

of investigation by including male nurses from various hospitals and healthcare settings. The inclusion of participants from diverse backgrounds allows researchers to have a global meaning on the lives of male nurses. With this wider view, one can look into the factors that drive retention and work place dynamics in various healthcare environments better. It also makes knowledge gained useful to more health institutions when it combines outputs from many different settings.

Additionally, efforts should be made to diversify the sample by recruiting larger and more diverse participant groups. This entails including participants with varied demographic characteristics, such as age, years of professional experience, and specialty areas. Furthermore, recruiting participants with diverse professional backgrounds can provide a more holistic perspective on the challenges and opportunities faced by male nurses in different roles within the healthcare system. A larger and more diverse sample ensures that the findings are representative of the male nursing population and captures a wider range of perspectives, contributing to the richness and depth of the research.

Lastly, future researchers should pay close attention to contextual factors such as organizational culture and healthcare policies when interpreting findings. These contextual factors play a significant role in shaping male nurses' experiences and intentions within their workplace. Developing effective strategies for retaining men in nursing requires understanding the influence of organization culture, healthcare policies and leadership styles. By considering these contextual factors, researchers can provide more nuanced insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by male nurses and inform the development of targeted interventions to improve retention and workplace satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Regarding the conditions of this study, several ethical considerations were carefully addressed. Permission was secured from the hospital's administrator and head nurse through a letter of authorization, granting access to the institution's employees and establishing the researchers' credibility. An informed consent approach was employed to ensure that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose and design, with clear communication that participation was voluntary and they could withdraw at any time without consequence. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were rigorously maintained, and permission was obtained for audio recording the interviews. No conflicts of interest were present, and the study was conducted with strict avoidance of plagiarism. The researchers addressed potential biases through reflexivity, acknowledging how their backgrounds and experiences might influence the study. They ensured that the interpretation of the findings was unbiased and that the results were used solely for research purposes, demonstrating their commitment to ethical research practices.

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